

Associations between Specific Antinuclear Antibodies, detected by Line Immunoassay, and Clinical Features of Patients with Systemic Lupus Erythematosus

Mohamed A. Hefny¹, Nahed I. Gomaa², Amal Fathy³ and Sherief Labib⁴

Departments of ¹Rheumatology & Rehabilitation, ²Microbiology & Immunology, ³Clinical pathology and ⁴Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine-Suez Canal University

Background: Autoantibodies are an integral part of the process of classifying, detecting, and, at least in some cases, mediating autoimmune diseases. The antinuclear antibody is not just one antibody but, actually, many different antibodies associated with a variety of diseases and disease manifestations. Antinuclear antibodies (ANA), anti-Sm, or anti-dsDNA antibodies are part of the American College of Rheumatology criteria (ACR) for SLE. Specific reactivities are associated with distinct clinical features of SLE.

Objectives: To study associations between antinuclear antibodies (ANA) detected by Line Immunoassay and signs/symptoms in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE).

Methods: A total of 38 unselected consecutive patients, diagnosed as having SLE and attending the rheumatology and nephrology units, Suez Canal University Hospital, were included in this study. The patients met the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) revised criteria for classification of SLE. ANA profiles were determined by line immunoassay and by indirect immunofluorescence on *Critidia luciliae*. An extensive list of signs/symptoms was evaluated.

Results: ANA were found by indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) in 36/38 (95%) patients. The frequencies of the specific reactivities were: anti-dsDNA 60%, anti-SmB 35%, anti-SmD 25%, anti-RNP-C 25%, anti-Ro60 15%, anti-SSB 15%, anti-RNP-A 10%, antiRibosomal P 10%, anti-Ro52 5%, anti Cnp-B 5%, anti Scl-70 2.6%, and anti-Histones 60%. Cutaneous manifestations were associated with anti-SSB, Ro52, Ribosomal P, anti-dsDNA and histones. Raynaud's phenomenon was associated with Ro52 and 60, histones and RNP-C. Xerostomia was associated with Ro52 and 60 as well as Cnp-B. Renal manifestations were associated with RNP-A, Ro52, Ro60 and dsDNA.

Conclusion: By using a sensitive and specific multiparameter assay like LIA for identifying antinuclear reactivities, we could confirm some of the previously reported associations of antibodies with clinical symptoms of SLE. We also found several new associations meriting further study.

INTRODUCTION

A humoral autoimmune response is a common manifestation of the rheumatic connective tissue diseases (CTD) and often includes antinuclear antibodies (ANA) (1). Autoantibodies are an integral part of the process of classifying, detecting, and, at least in some cases, mediating autoimmune diseases. Since the discovery of the antinuclear antibody more than 40 years ago, it has been closely associated with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). Yet the antinuclear antibody is not just one antibody but, actually, many different antibodies associated with a variety of diseases and disease manifestations (2).

Systemic lupus erythematosus, the prototype of systemic autoimmune disorders, has been considered for many years a classic model of immune complex mediated disease. However, earlier data demonstrate that multilevel dysfunction of cellular and humoral immunity underlie the

pathophysiology of the disorder. The expression and clinical course of SLE vary enormously from very mild, with arthralgias and skin rashes, to life threatening, when the renal and central nervous system function are severely compromised; from complete quiescence to full blown expression of the disease (3).

Antinuclear antibodies (ANA), anti-Sm, or anti-dsDNA antibodies are part of the American College of Rheumatology criteria (ACR) for SLE (4, 5). Specific reactivities are associated with distinct clinical features of SLE. Known associations are anti-dsDNA antibodies with lupus nephritis, anti-SSA and anti-SSB antibodies with sicca symptoms, and anti-RNP antibodies with Raynaud's phenomenon (6). More associations have been described, but different studies yield conflicting results (7).

Indirect immunofluorescence (IIF) on human epitheloid cells (HEp-2 cells) is the classically used technique for the detection of

ANA (8). Positive fluorescence staining indicates the presence of ANA but does not allow precise identification of these autoantibodies. For that purpose, additional testing is required, employing techniques such as immunoprecipitation in agar, western immunoblotting (1), enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (9) or, the more recently developed, line immunoassay (LIA) (10). Because a characteristic profile of ANA is associated with most CTD, identification of the fine specificity may provide valuable clues to the diagnosis (11).

In this study we analysed serum samples from SLE patients referred to our laboratory for ANA testing. Further identification of the fine reactivity of these antibodies was obtained with IIF on *Crithidia* (for the detection of anti-dsDNA antibodies), and by line immunoassay (for detection of anti-nuclear antibodies subtypes). Also, we designed this study to evaluate associations of specific ANA, detected by LIA, and clinical features in patients with SLE

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

A total of 38 unselected consecutive patients, diagnosed as having SLE and attending the rheumatology and nephrology units, Suez Canal University Hospital, were included in this study. The patients met the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) revised criteria for classification of SLE (Hochberg, 1997). The female to male ratio was 8:1. The mean age was 26 years (range 15-45). A questionnaire covering the clinical data was completed. The questionnaire was an extension of the ACR criteria for SLE (table 1). The study was conducted after approval by the local ethics committees. Informed consent was obtained from all patients.

Blood samples were drawn and allowed to clot for about 30 minutes at room temperature. Sera were obtained by centrifugation and stored in aliquots at -20°C until tested. The studied group was subjected to the routine investigations for SLE patients including :

- Urine analysis for assessment of proteinuria, haematuria, pyuria and urinary casts.
- Complete blood picture

- Estimation of serum level of complement3 (C3) was done by single immunodiffusion using Diffu-plate complement C3 (Biocientifica, S.A., Argentina).

They were also subjected to ANA and anti-dsDNA testing by indirect immunofluorescence on HEp-2 and on *Crithidia Luciliae* respectively and extractable nuclear antigens (ENA) detection by Line immunoassay.

Indirect Immunofluorescence on HEP-2.

Serum diluted 1/40 in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) was overlaid onto fixed HEp-2 cells (Diasorin, Minnesota, USA) for 30 minutes at room temperature. Slides were washed twice for five minutes each with PBS, overlaid with fluorescence labeled conjugate, which is antihuman IgG, and incubated for an additional 30 minutes. After washing twice, a cover slip was placed over the slide, and the slides were read using a fluorescence microscope at ×40 power.

Indirect Immunofluorescence on CRITHIDIA LUCILIAE

Crithidia luciliae coated slides (Diasorin, Minnesota, USA) were used for the detection of anti-dsDNA. Serum samples diluted 1/20 in PBS were incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature. Slides were washed twice for five minutes each with PBS, overlaid with fluorescence labeled conjugate, which is antihuman IgG and incubated for an additional 30 minutes. After washing twice, a cover slip was placed over the slide, and the slides were read using a fluorescence microscope at ×40 power.

Line Immunoassay (LIA)

Serum samples were analysed by LIA (INNO-LIA ANA Update, Innogenetics, Belgium). This assay contains the following recombinant antigens (SmB, RNP-70k, RNP-A, RNP-C, Ro52, La/SSB, Cenp-B, Topo-I, Jo-1), synthetic peptides (SmD and ribosomal P) and natural proteins (Ro60 and histones). These extractable nuclear antigens are coated as discrete lines on a nylon strip with plastic backing. In addition one control line is coated on each strip.

The test was performed according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, the

nylon strips were incubated with serum at a 1/200 dilution. If autoantibodies are present in the sample they will bind to the specific antigen lines on the strip. A goat antihuman IgG labeled with alkaline phosphatase was allowed to bind to the antigen-antibody complex. The enzyme substrate and chromogen 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl phosphatase (BCIP) produces a dark brown color in proportion to the amount of specific autoantibody in the test sample. Sulphuric acid stops the color development. If the sample doesn't contain specific autoantibodies, the labeled anti-human antibody will not bind to autoantibody/antigen complex and only the control line and a low background color will appear.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 10.0 (Chicago, IL, USA). To determine associations between autoantibodies and symptoms, one-way

ANOVA test was used to produce a one-way analysis of variance for a quantitative dependent variable by a single factor variable (SLE symptoms versus autoantibodies presence). A p value ≤ 0.05 was taken to indicate significance.

RESULTS

Presence of ANA (Fig.1)

ANA were found by IIF in 36/38 (95%) patients. The frequencies of the specific reactivities were: anti-dsDNA 60%, anti-SmB 35%, anti-SmD 25%, anti-RNP-C 25%, anti-Ro60 15%, anti-SSB 15%, anti-RNP-A 10%, antiRibosomal P 10%, anti-Ro52 5%, anti Cenp-B 5%, anti Scl-70 2.6%, and anti-Histones 60%. Antibodies to RNP-70 and Jo-1 were not detected in our study.

Figure 1: LIA for 18 samples (strips 2 to 19). Strip 1 is the positive control with all the antigens and control line

Presence of clinical symptoms

Table (1) lists the frequencies of clinical symptoms. The most common manifestations were: Headache, Fatigue,

arthritis, alopecia, malar rash, proteinuria, photosensitivity and anemia with a frequency ranging from 85% to 50%.

Table 1: The frequencies of clinical symptoms

Symptoms	Frequency(%)
Cutaneous manifestations	
Malar rash	65
Discoid rash	5
Photosensitivity	55
Alopecia	70
Mouth ulcers	40
Genital ulcers	25
Sicca symptoms	
Xerostomia	20
Xerophthalmia	15
General symptoms	
Fatigue	80
Weight loss	45
Fever	45
Raynaud's phenomenon	30
Musculoskeletal	
Arthritis	75
Myalgia	30
Serositis	25
Chest pain	40
Renal symptoms	
Proteinuria	60
Casts	30
Neurological	
Lupus Headache	85
Seizures	5
Cerebrovascular accidents (CVA)	10
Psychosis	15
Chorea	25
Hematological	
Leukopenia	30
Thrombocytopenia	10
Anemia	50
Others	
Hemoptysis	5
Epistaxis	10
Angioneurotic edema	15
Recurrent abortion	15

Associations of antibodies with symptoms

Table (2) lists significant associations between ANA Subtypes and clinical symptoms. Results from the study showed that most of the ANA subtypes were associated with clinical symptoms especially anti-Ro52, Ro60, SSB and Scl-70 which showed a multiplicity of symptoms associated with significant correlations as seen in table

(2). Cutaneous manifestations were associated with anti-SSB, Ro52, Ribosomal P, anti-dsDNA and histones. Raynaud's phenomenon was associated with Ro52 and Ro60, histones and RNP-C. Xerostomia was associated with Ro52 and Ro60 as well as Cenp-B. Renal manifestations were associated with RNP-A, Ro52, Ro60 and dsDNA.

Table 2: Significant associations between ANA Subtypes and clinical symptoms

ANA Subtypes	Clinical Symptoms							
		P value		P value		P value		P value
SmB	Seizures	0.04						
SmD	Seizures	0.008						
RNP-A	Epistaxis	0.03	Seizures	0.047	Casts	0.04		
RNP-C	Raynaud's							
Ro52	Raynaud's	0.022	Cellular Casts	0.022	Xerostomia	0.01	Genital Ulcers	0.008
Ro60	Raynaud's	0.02	Cellular Casts	0.02	Xerostomia	0.04	Fever	0.039
La/SSB	Fever	0.039	Genital Ulcers	0.01	Psychosis	0.04		
Cenp-B	Xerostomia	0.042						
Scl-70	Hemoptysis	0.42	CVA	0.042	Abortions	0.028	Oral Ulcers	0.004
Ribosomal-P	Discoïd Rash	0.001	Genital Ulcers	0.008	Seizures	0.048		
Histones	Raynaud's	0.015	Oral Ulcers	0.042				
dsDNA	casts	0.004	Chorea	0.036	Photosensitivity	0.024	arthritis	0.032

P significant < 0.05

DISCUSSION

The generation of autoantibodies is an important feature of SLE. Several studies have demonstrated that specific ANA are associated with different symptoms of SLE (6). More associations have been described, but different studies yield conflicting results (7). Several studies described these associations between different racial and ethnical groups but few were done on Arabs especially Egyptians. In this study, we tried to draw a profile for SLE Egyptian patients by associating their clinical manifestations with ANA subtypes. An extensive list of signs and symptoms was evaluated.

In our study, we used a multiparameter assay (LIA) as a more sensitive technique than immunodiffusion (11), and this also allowed the detection of fine reactivities to the different determinants of Sm (SmB and SmD), RNP (RNP-A, RNP-C, and RNP-70k) and SSA (Ro52 and Ro60) (10,12).

By using the LIA for detection of individual anti-ANAs, results revealed the incidence of anti-Sm antibodies, one of the ACR criteria for SLE diagnosis as 35% for SmB and 25% for SmD. These results

confirm the statement of Tan *et al.* (13) and Von Duijnhoven *et al.* (14) that the presence of anti-Sm antibodies is a marker for diagnosis of SLE. Our results go in agreement with the results of Lock and Unsworth (15) who found an incidence of 34% among their patients. Also, our results were nearly the same when compared to the study done by Ghedira *et al.* (16) on 128 SLE patients in Tunisia.

Regarding the anti-La/SSB antibodies, we found an incidence of 15% which comes in agreement with the results reported by Meheus and his group (10) and Tamara *et al.* (12).

Anti-Scl-70 antibodies, one of the disease markers used in confirming the diagnosis of scleroderma, was found in only one case and this result was also reported in another study done on 43 Egyptian SLE patients (12). This result can be accepted knowing that anti-Scl-70 is not usually found in SLE patients as confirmed by Hildebrandt *et al.* (17). They stated that these antibodies were rarely found in SLE and mixed connective tissue disease patients. On the contrary, Gussin *et al.* (18) reported that anti-Scl-70 were present in a significant subset of patients with SLE and for this subset of

patients they offered a good correlate of disease activity and suggested increased risk for pulmonary hypertension and nephritis.

Concerning the antiribosomal P antibodies, the incidence was 10% which was in concordance to the studies of Damoiseaux *et al.* (19), Hoffman *et al.* (20) and Gerli *et al.* (21) who reported an incidence of 10%, 12 % and 12% respectively.

As regards Jo-1 antibodies, it was not detected in our study which was the same in the study of Damoiseaux *et al.* (19). Also, Hoffman *et al.* (20) reported a low incidence of 1.3%.

The anti-Ro antibodies were detected in 15% and 5% of patients (Ro60 and Ro52 respectively). This goes in agreement with the study of Zimmerman *et al.* (22) but was lower than the results of Hoffman *et al.* (20).

When looking at the other ANAs, our results were different from those of Hoffman *et al.* (20). The above similarities or differences in ANAs frequencies between our study and the other studies mentioned above should be interpreted cautiously because of the different population studied and the different methods used for ANAs testing.

Previous studies found that anti-Sm antibodies were associated with oral ulcers and sicca symptoms (7). Thompson *et al.* (6) found that they were associated with malar rash, renal involvement and blood manifestations while Lopez-Longo *et al.* (23) found an association with Raynaud's phenomenon. We could not confirm these associations as seen in table (2) but the only association with anti-Sm antibodies was found with seizures and there is no published data about this association and it might be a coincidence and needs further studies on a larger population since seizures occurred in 5% only of patients.

We confirmed the previously reported association between anti-RNP antibodies and Raynaud's phenomenon (24, 20). A significant association was found also between RNP-A and seizures, epistaxis and urinary cellular casts. Urinary cellular casts association with individual RNP subparticles is concomitant with the study of Bastian *et al.* (25). Associations of renal disease with anti-RNP antibodies have been reported but remain controversial (25). In another study, both anti-RNP-A and RNP-C antibodies were

associated with a lower risk for urine cellular casts (20). Al Attia *et al.* (26) found no association between these auto-antibodies and lupus nephritis. The presence of seizures can be explained as coincidence but the relation with epistaxis can be explained by the fact that those patients might have uncontrolled elevated blood pressure which is a well known cause of epistaxis.

It is well known that there are associations of anti-SSA antibodies (defined as antibodies to Ro52 or Ro60) with xerostomia and xerophthalmia (10). In our study this association was found significant with xerostomia only. Looking at the individual antibodies we found a significant association between Raynaud's phenomena, cellular casts, psychosis and genital ulcers and the presence of anti-Ro52 antibodies. In relation to anti-Ro60 antibodies, we found a significant association with Raynaud's phenomena, cellular casts, psychosis and fever.

In our study there were association between anti-SSB antibodies and fever, psychosis and genital ulcers which differs totally from the previous confirmations of the association between anti-SSB antibodies and xerostomia, xerophthalmia and pericarditis (20).

Concerning antiribosomal P antibodies, associations were found with genital ulcers, seizures and discoid rash and this differs from the published studies which confirmed associations of antiribosomal P antibodies and haematological disorders (27) and more precisely with haemolytic anaemia and leukopenia. The association between antiribosomal P and discoid rash has been described previously in the study of Gerli *et al.* (21).

Finally, considering antihistone antibodies, we found an association with Raynaud's phenomena and oral ulcers which needs to be confirmed.

Concerning the presence of anti-dsDNA, associations were found between its presence and the occurrence of fatigue, casts, photosensitivity and arthritis. The association with renal involvement was described before in the study of Hoffman *et al.* (20) and Ghedira *et al.* (16). They also reported an association with arthritis which is consistent with our results.

In conclusion, by using a sensitive and specific multiparameter assay like LIA for identifying antinuclear reactivities, we could confirm some of the previously reported associations of antibodies with clinical symptoms of SLE. We also found several new associations meriting further study. In interpreting these associations and comparing it to previous studies we must pay attention that ethnical difference plays a role in both clinical and serological profiles of SLE patients and that the clinical manifestations associated with these antibodies in same SLE patients vary according to the technique used.

REFERENCES

1. Von Mühlen, C.A. and Tan, E.M. (1995): Autoantibodies in the diagnosis of systemic rheumatic diseases. *Semin. Arthritis Rheum.* 24:323-358.
2. Shmerling, R.H. (2003): Autoantibodies in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. *There before You Know It. N. Engl. J. Med.* 16: 349.
3. Oelke, K. and Richardson, B. (2002): Pathogenesis of lupus. *Arthritis Rheum.* 47:343-5.
4. Tan, E.M.; Cohen, A.S.; Fries, J.F, *et al.* (1982): The 1982 revised criteria for the classification of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Arthritis Rheum.* 25: 1271-1277.
5. Hochberg, M.C. (1997): Updating the American College of Rheumatology revised criteria for the classification of systemic lupus erythematosus [letter]. *Arthritis Rheum.* 40: 1725.
6. Thompson, D.; Juby, A.; Davis, P. (1993): The clinical significance of autoantibody profiles in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus* 2:15-19.
7. Cervera, R.; Khamasta, M.A.; Font, J. *et al.* (1993): Systemic lupus erythematosus: clinical and immunologic patterns of disease expression in a cohort of 1000 patients. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 72:113-24.
8. Humbel, R.L.: Detection of antinuclear antibodies by immunofluorescence. In: Van Venrooij, W.J.; Maini, R.N., eds. *Manual of biological markers of disease.* Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic, 1993; A21-16.
9. Tan, E.M.; Smolen, J.S.; Mc Dougal, J.S. *et al.* (1999): A critical evaluation of enzyme immunoassays for detection of antinuclear antibodies of defined specificities. *Arthritis Rheum.* 42:455-464.
10. Meheus, L.; Van Venrooij, W.J.; Wiik, A. *et al.* (1997): Determination of the fine specificity of antinuclear antibodies in connective tissue diseases using a multiparameter line immunoassay (LIA) based on recombinant proteins. *Clin. Exp. Rheumatol.* 17:205-214.
11. Peene, I.; Meheus, L.; Veys, E.M. *et al.* (2001): Detection and identification of antinuclear antibodies (ANA) in a large and consecutive cohort of serum samples referred for ANA testing. *Ann. Rheum. Dis.* 60:1131-1136.
12. Tamara, M.F.; El-Shawarby, L.A.; Galal, Z.A. *et al.* (2002): Detection of antibodies to extractable nuclear antigens: comparative evaluation of different methods. *Egyptian J. Immunol.* 9(1): 103-109.
13. Tan, E.; Chan, E.; Sullivan, K. *et al.* (1988): Antinuclear antibodies: Diagnostically specific immune markers and clues toward the understanding of systemic autoimmunity. *Clin. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 47:121-141.
14. Van Duijnshoven, H.L.; Van de Warenburg, F.J.; Willems, R.J. *et al.* (1999): A comparison of ELISA assays as routine diagnostic test for detection of autoantibodies against extractable nuclear antigens. *Clin. Biochem.* 32: 179-183.
15. Lock, R.J. and Unsworth, D.J. (2001): Antibodies to extractable nuclear antigens. Has technological drift affected clinical interpretation? *J. Clin. Pathol.* 54: 187-190.
16. Ghedira, I.; Sakly, W. and Jeddi, M. (2002): Clinical and serological characteristics of systemic lupus erythematosus: 128 cases. *Pathol. Biol.* 50(1):18-24.
17. Hiderbrandt, S.; Weiner, E.S.; Senecal, J.L. *et al.* (1990): Antibodies to Topoisomerase 1: analysis by gel diffusion, immunoblot and ELISA. *Clin. Immunol. Immunopathol.* 57: 399-410.

18. Gussin, H.; Ignat, G.; Varga, J. *et al.* (2001): Antibodies to Topoisomerase 1 in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Arthritis Rheumatol.* 44 (2): 376-383.
19. Damoiseaux, J.; Boesten, K.; Giesen, J. *et al.* (2005): Evaluation of a Novel Line-Blot Immunoassay for the Detection of Antibodies to Extractable Nuclear Antigens. *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.* 1050: 340-347.
20. Hoffman, I.; Peene, I.; Meheus, L. *et al.* (2004): Specific antinuclear antibodies are associated with clinical features in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann. Rheum. Dis.* 63:1155-1158.
21. Gerli, R.; Caponi, L. and Tincani, A. (2002): Clinical and serological associations of ribosomal P autoantibodies in systemic lupus erythematosus: prospective evaluation in a large cohort of Italian patients *Rheumatology* 41: 1357-1366.
22. Zimmerman, C.; Smolen, J.S.; Graninger, W. *et al.* (1996): Fine specificity of anti-Ro (SSA) autoantibodies and clinical manifestations in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *J. Rheumatol.* 23:1897-903.
23. Lopez-Longo, F.J.; Gonzalez Fernandez, C.M.; Rodriguez Mahou, M. *et al.* (1997): Clinical expression of systemic lupus erythematosus with anti-U1-RNP and anti-Sm antibodies. *Rev. Clin. Esp.* 197(5):329-35.
24. Luyckx, A.; Westhovens, R.; Oris, E. *et al.* (2005): Clinical Relevance of Measurement of Antibodies to Individual snU₁-RNP Proteins. *Clinical Chemistry.* 51:1888-1890.
25. Bastian, H.M.; Roseman, J.M.; McGwin, G. *et al.* (2002): Systemic lupus erythematosus in three ethnic groups. XII. Risk factors for lupus nephritis after diagnosis. *Lupus* 11:152-60.
26. AL Attia, H.M.; Al Ahmed, Y.H. and Chandani, A.U. (1998): Serological markers in Arabs with lupus nephritis. *Lupus.* 7(3):198-201.
27. Isenberg, D.A.; Garton, M.; Reichlin, M.W. *et al.* (1997): Long-term follow-up of autoantibody profiles in black female lupus patients and clinical comparison with Causcasian and Asian patients. *Br. J. Rheumatol.* 36:229-33.

